

Car Price Prediction Using Machine Learning - Linear Regression

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Abstract—Car price prediction is an intriguing research issue that necessitates a great deal of information and work. The production of vehicles has increased at a rapid rate in recent decades, resulting in the car market being a huge business. The recent advent of online platforms has reinforced the requirement for both the users and the sellers to be updated about the current market trends regarding the topic. We are using Machine Learning Algorithm Linear Regression, The mission is to develop an efficient and accurate model to predict the price of a used car, based on a given set of traits. We take parameters of car like: Company name, Model name, Year of Purchase, Fuel Type and Number of Kilometers it has been driven and then predicts the possible price of the vehicle.

Keywords—Car Price Prediction, Linear regression, Machine learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The used car market is growing at a rapid pace, In the last few years, its market value has nearly doubled. The rise of online portals like Carwale, Quikr, Cars24, CarDheko and others has emphasized the need for both customers and sellers to be more knowledgeable about market trends and patterns that affect the price of a used car. Machine Learning algorithms can be utilized to calculate the retail value of a car based on some predetermined parameters.

II. DESCRIPTION

It's tough to determine the resale value of a used vehicle. The majority of the population are unaware that the price of a used car is decided by a variety of factors. Usually the most essential factors are usually the vehicle's age, horsepower, provenance (the native country of the manufacturers), mileage (the amount of distance travelled), and make(model). Because of rising fuel prices, gasoline economy is becoming increasingly important. Unfortunately, most people have no clue on how much fuel their vehicle utilizes each kilometre travelled in real life.

The type of fuel, interior design, braking mechanism, speed increase, chamber volume, safety profile, car size, number of doors, paint tone/color, buyer audits, renown achievements which were won by the car manufacturers, the vehicle's current state, if it's a sports vehicle, if journey control is implemented or not, if the vehicle is manual transmission or it is programmed, and if it has a place with an individual or an corporation are all things to think about. Mauritius purchasers value the location of previous owners, whether or not the vehicle has been involved in big accidents, and whether or not it is a woman-driven vehicle. The design and feel of the car have a significant impact on the price.As can be seen, the price is prohibitively high.

Programming applications that use artificial intelligence (AI) can improve precision rates in general without being specifically tailored to do as such. Linear regression is an excellent approach for forecasting the future that is based on science. It anticipates continuous/genuine or quantitative components and shows direct connection transit, which examines how the value of the dependent variable changes with respect to the value of the independent variables.

Regression Algorithms like linear regression are utilized because they produce a continuous value rather than a classified value as an output. As a result, rather than predicting the price range of a vehicle, it will be feasible to anticipate the actual worth of a car. A user interface is created using Flask which takes input from the user and displays the price of the vehicle based on the user inputs.

A. Some Key facts

- The Company name, Model name, Year of Purchase, Fuel Type and Number of Kilometers driven are all some attributes which can influence the value of the car.
- The characteristics that affect the car's pricing may differ by region and are difficult to predict precisely.
- Because trends changes quickly and since everyone has distinct likes and dislikes, modifying a car may have a negative effect on its worth.

B. Machine Learning

Machine learning is an area of computer science that allows machines to understand without having to be programmed directly. Machine learning is amongst the most fascinating technology that has ever been discovered. It gives the computer the capacity to learn, making it more sentient, as the name implies. Machine learning is being used currently in considerably more places than one might expect.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine learning are gaining a lot of traction around the world. Artificial Intelligence's variety of uses has altered the face of technology. The phrases Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning are sometimes used interchangeably.

AI may be viewed from three angles: I) The computer calculation used to make a decision, ii) The criteria and traits that should go into making a decision, ii) For base data, the response is known, which facilitates (readies) the system to develop.[4]

III. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The major objective of this project is to develop a machine learning model which can accurately anticipate scenarios in order to evaluate a used car's resale value based on its attributes and make suitable conclusions. Using a data set of sales pricing for multiple manufacturers and models to train numerous learning algorithms.

IV. LITERATURE SURVEY

Various studies have looked into how to predict the price of a used vehicle. Enis Gegic [1] uses three different machine learning techniques - Random Forest(RF), Support Vector Machine(SVM) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) to build the model to predict the price of the car. The performances of each algorithms were compared to find which suits better for the data set. Then the model is integrated into a java applicaion.

Nitis Monburinon and his colleagues [2] conducted a comparative study on performance of regression based on supervised machine learning models This includes gradient boosted regression trees, multiple linear regression and random forest regression. Performance with each model is checked and mean absolute error is calculated.

Praful Rane [3] stresses about how both seller and buyer has no idea about the car and it's worth in the present day scenario. To overcome this a model is developed using various regression algorithms like linear regression, lasso regression and ridge regression to get an accurate prediction.

Rosemol thomas and rini kurian [4] also follows a similar path and employs regression algorithms such as linear regression and lasso regression, focusing on the differences between the two.

Ravi Shastri [5] utilizes randomized search CV, random forest regression and multiple linear regression analysis. The predictions are then checked and compared to find that results yielded similar values.

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V. METHODOLOGY

There are two basic stages in the system:

1. Training stage: The system is trained to fit the model (line/curve) with the suitable algorithm chosen based on the values from the data set.
2. During the testing stage, the system is put through its paces and put through various tests to check if its efficient and working. The precision has been double-checked. To model or test it, it must be appropriate.

A. Pycharm

PyCharm is a dedicated Python Integrated Development Environment (IDE) that includes a variety of critical utilities for Python programmers and developers that are tightly integrated to provide a comfortable workspace for effective Python, data science and web development.

B. Pycharm Features

PyCharm offers code inspections, smart code completion, on-the-fly mistake flagging and quick fixes, as well as rich navigation and automated code refactorings.

- Intelligent Code Editor: PyCharm's smart code editor provides the best support for Python, CSS, JavaScript, TypeScript, CoffeeScript, famous template languages and more.
- Smart Code Navigation: PyCharm's clever smart search can be used to quickly navigate to any class, folder, or symbol, as well as any IDE action or tool window.
- Fast and Safe Refactorings: With safe Rename and Delete, Extract Method, Inline Variable or Method, Introduce Variable, and more code refactoring, you may refactor your code intelligently.
- Debugging, Profiling and Testing: For Python and JavaScript, users can utilize the sophisticated debugger with an excellent graphical user interface.
- Database tools: MySQL, SQL Server, PostgreSQL, Oracle, and other databases can be accessed directly from the IDE.

C. Flask

Flask is a lightweight and compact Python web framework that provides fundamental features and tools for building innovative Python applications. It provides developers more variety and is a more enticing framework for novice developers because you can quickly construct a web application using only a single Python file.

Flask boasts features including Development server and debugger, Integrated support for unit testing,Google App Engine compatibility to name a few.

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

On our data set, we're employing the Linear Regression approach to construct or refine an appropriate and efficient model for predicting the price of used vehicles.

A. Data collection

We'll look at a data set from the Kaggle repository that provides information about secondhand vehicles. The price of a used car is predicted depending on a number of factors. Important factors which determines the value or price of the used car is included in the Kaggle data collection. This data is cleaned thoroughly.[5]

Table 1: Attributes and its Values

Input Attributes	Function/Values
Car_Name	Name of the car.
company	Company of the car.
year	Year in which the car was bought.
Price	The price owner wants to sell the car.
kms_driven	The distance covered by the car in km.
fuel_type	Fuel type of the car.

B. Algorithm

Linear regression algorithm is amongst the most fundamental and extensively used Machine Learning techniques. It's an approach of conducting predictive analysis using statistics.

The linear regression algorithm gives a linear relationship between a dependent variable (y) and one or more independent variables (x), hence the name. Since linear regression illustrates a linear relationship, it may explain how the dependent variable's value changes with respect to the changes of independent variable's value.

Fig 1: Representation of linear regression

From Fig 1, linear regression can be represented in the form:

$$y = a_0 + a_1x + \epsilon$$

Here, x = Independent Variable (predictor Variable),

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y = Dependent Variable (Target Variable),

ϵ = random error,

a1 = Linear regression coefficient,

a0= line intercept.

The values for the x and y parameters are training datasets for the representation of a Linear Regression model.

Fig2 : flask user interface

Fig3: Prediction is given according to the user inputs

Car Price Prediction

This app lets you to predict the price of the car you need. fill the details below:

Select the company:
Audi

Select the model:
Audi A4 2.0

Select Year of Purchase:
2014

Select the Fuel Type:
Diesel

Enter the Number of Kilometres that the car has travelled:
31000

Predict Price

Prediction: ₹1598785.61 and rent for the car is 63951.4244

VII. CONCLUSION

The resale of used cars is a rapidly expanding industry. Because of the increase in the price of automobiles and consumers inability to afford them, car resales are also increasing all around the world. As a result, a system that precisely anticipates the value of a used automobile and determines the car's price formed on a variety of parameters is urgently needed. The recommended system will assist in the precise determination of a price forecast for a used car.

VIII. REFERENCES

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